

USE OF SURFACTANTS IN OIL PRODUCTION

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ANNOTATION. 30 commercial surfactants were tested to select the best candidate. First, phase behavior screening was used as a quick and effective method by which to identify favorable surfactant formulations. This involved observing the equilibrium time, microemulsion viscosity, oil and water solubilization ratio, and IFT. Then, the spinning drop test was used to measure the IFT for the different oil/brine/surfactant systems as a supplement to the phase behavior test.

KEYWORDS: surfactant formulations, solubilization, identify potential, determine, optimal salinity, istiqbolli narsani, acquire samples.

INTRODUCTION. Identify promising surfactant enhanced oil recovery formulations. This study was performed under ambient temperatures; different kinds of surfactants (i.e., anionic, cationic and nonionic surfactants) were investigated. The following steps were taken to identify promising surfactant enhanced oil recovery EOR formulations:

- Use knowledge of surfactant chemistry and commercial surfactant production capabilities to identify potential surfactant test candidates.

- Acquire samples from surfactant companies and screen the acquired surfactants using the phase behavior experiment.
- Observe the viscosity of the oil/surfactant/brine microemulsion in order to avoid high-viscous phases.
- Determine the IFT for oil/brine/surfactant systems using a spinning drop tensiometer.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY. Identification of potential surfactant test candidates. Extensive research on surfactants has established a clear relationship between the surfactant structure and the reservoir fluid properties. For instance, an increased hydrophobe length for surfactants is accompanied by both a decreased optimal salinity and an increased solubilization ratio. Furthermore, adding weakly hydrophobic function groups, i.e., propylene oxide (PO) will increase the range of the ultra-low IFT region. In contrast, adding ethylene oxide (EO) groups increases both the hydrophilic properties and the optimal salinity. [1, 2].

Varying the number of PO groups and EO groups will cause the surfactant to exhibit varying ratios of the hydrophilic-lipophilic balance (HLB). The HLB can be used to identify the surfactant properties. As described by Griffin, an HLB value less than 10 indicates strong hydrophobic properties, while a value greater than 10 indicates strong hydrophilic properties. An HLB value from 11 to 14 indicates good wetting agent properties. Based on previous information and prior work in this field, 30 different surfactants were selected to undergo the phase behavior screening. [3, 4].

The formation of separate, thermodynamically stable phases when surfactant, oil and brine are mixed was first illustrated by Winsor. Winsor phase behavior is a distinction among the three phase behaviors of oil, water and surfactant systems when they form a microemulsion.

Effect of salinity on phase behavior. A transition in phase behavior can be caused by altering a variable such as the salinity, surfactant structure, temperature, or equivalent alkane carbon number (EACN) of the oil. [5].

The salinity of the brine phase is an important parameter influencing which type of Winsor phase behavior occurs. At low salinity, Type I, or oil-in-water, microemulsions occur; these are characterized by coexistence with an excess brine phase. At very high salinity, Type II, or water-in-oil, microemulsions are formed, which are characterized by coexistence with an excess oil phase. [6, 7]. A narrow intermediate range exists between the Type I and Type II regions in which oil and water microemulsions are formed as a middle phase and coexist with both excess oil and excess water phases. These are referred to as Type III microemulsions. The salinities at which the transition occurs between Type I and Type III behavior is referred to as the lower critical salinity, and the salinity of the transition between Type III and Type II is referred to as the upper critical salinity. [5, 7].

DISCUSSION. The salinity at which equal volumes of oil and water are solubilized in the microemulsion is defined as the optimal salinity. The ratios V_o/V_s and V_w/V_s increase and decrease with salinity, respectively. When these ratios are plotted, the intersection point within the Type III salinity range is the optimum solubilization ratio at the optimum salinity.

Optimal salinity also has been defined as the salinity at which the IFT between the microemulsion and water equals the IFT between the microemulsion and oil; it is typically the same or nearly the same as the optimal salinity for equal solubilization. The optimal salinity lies approximately at the midpoint between the lower critical salinity and the upper critical salinity.

The optimum solubilization ratio corresponds to the lowest IFT, which is the desired condition for mobilizing oil in EOR. Optimum solubilization ratios for specified oils will vary for different surfactants and their mixtures. However, a high optimum solubilization ratio is not sufficient to yield acceptable behavior and high oil recovery. The absence of viscous phases such as gels, liquid crystals and macroemulsions and short equilibration times are equally important.

Healy & Reed developed an empirical correlation between the solubilization ratios and IFT between the microemulsion and each excess phase. A simplified form of his theory predicts that the IFT (a) is inversely proportional to the square of the solubilization ratio (S^2).

$$a = C/S^2$$

In this equation, C is approximately 0.30 dynes/cm, and the solubilization ratio (s) is defined as the volume of solubilized oil or water divided by the volume of surfactant on a 100% active basis. The solubilization ratio is much more easily and accurately measured over time than IFT and therefore serves as a useful surrogate for measuring IFT directly.

Achieving ultra-low IFT on the order of 10⁻³ dynes/cm is necessary to mobilize the residual oil saturation in reservoir rocks and to reduce the oil saturation towards

zero under typical pressure gradients in oil reservoirs. However, additional conditions must be satisfied for surfactant flooding to be both efficient and practical under reservoir conditions. In order to transport surfactant solutions at low pressure gradients (~1 psi/ft) encountered in typical oil reservoirs, highly viscous phases must be avoided.

Phase behavior screening experiments were performed to evaluate the phase behavior of surfactant/oil/water mixtures at 1.00 wt% NaCl and 2,000 ppm surfactant solution. 7.00 ml of surfactant solution and 7.00 ml of synthetic oil (decane) were pipetted, as shown in Figure 3.2. The pipettes then were inverted several times to facilitate mixing. Phase behavior was observed and recorded over time. If the formation of macroemulsions appeared to inhibit mass transfer, the pipettes sometimes were agitated again.

The phase behavior of the surfactant system was evaluated using the following mostly qualitative criteria:

- How fast the emulsions break after gentle mixing and form a microemulsion in equilibrium with oil and/or brine
- The absence of macroemulsions

Interfacial tension measurements results. The spinning drop tensiometer apparatus results supported the phase behavior screening outcome by identifying both Alforterra 145-4S and Alforterra 145-8S as high-performance EOR surfactants under the required conditions. Figure 1. shows the IFT values for the most promising surfactants..

The best IFT result among the nonionic surfactants was 0.16 mN/m for Tomadol

45-13 with an HLB of 14.40 and 13.00 moles of EO. The anionic surfactant Alfoterra 145-8S (8 moles PO) showed an ultra-low IFT of less than 0.001 mN/m.

Figure 1. Effect of Number of Moles of (EO) on IFT for Neodol 25-N Series

Figure 2. Effect of Number of Moles of (EO) on IFT for Tergitol 15-S-N Series

Figure 3. Effect of Number of Moles of (EO) on IFT for Igepal CO-530, Tergitol NP-10, and Triton X-405 Surfactants

Figure 4. Effect of Number of Moles of (EO) on IFT for

Tomadol 45-N Series

CONCLUSION. For a series of nonionic surfactants at a constant salinity (1 wt. %) and constant surfactant concentration (0.2 wt. %), increasing the number of moles of EO was accompanied by a decrease in the IFT value. It was also observed that when the HLB exceeded 14.50, the IFT value increased even if the number of moles of EO increased, as shown in Figures 3.7. through 3.11. The HLB results for nonionic surfactants match Griffin's method. Griffin's method indicates that a nonionic surfactant with an HLB in the range of 11 to 14 is a good wetting agent, meaning that these surfactants can significantly reduce surface and interfacial tension and facilitate the spreading of a fluid over a surface.

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